

Some Aspects of Uptake of Manganese by Calcium Hydroxylapatite and the Effect of Such Incorporation on the Solubility of the Bone Mineral.

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The uptake of manganese by the synthetic calcium hydroxylapatite is facilitated by increase in Mn^{2+} concentration, a decrease in pH of medium of exchange and in the particle size of calcium hydroxylapatite. Absorption of Mn^{2+} and its accompanying diffusion into the interior of the crystals explain the mechanism of exchange.

CALCIUM hydroxylapatite $(CaHA)Ca_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2$ is the major inorganic component of human skeletal system¹ also called bone mineral. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic replacement reactions². $Ca^{2+} \rightarrow Mn^{2+}$ replacement in CaHA is of extreme biological significance as it explains the mechanism of incorporation of manganese into human skeletal system according to the following equation :

So the study of the uptake of manganese by CaHA and the effect of such incorporation on the solubility of bone mineral have been thoroughly investigated with synthetic samples and reported in this paper.

Experimental

Pure and homogeneous sample of CaHA² for the study of the dependence of uptake of manganese by CaHA and the samples of CaHA containing varying quantities of manganese in the form of solid solution³ for the study of the effect of incorporation of manganese in the solubility of bone mineral were prepared by co-precipitation a method specially worked out for this purpose⁴. The chemical composition of these samples were determined⁵.

The kinetics of $Ca^{2+} \rightarrow Mn^{2+}$ exchange and the dependence of uptake of manganese by CaHA on factors like pH concentration of Mn^{2+} ion, particle sizes were investigated. 0.2g of CaHA was equilibrated with a solution of 100 ml of $Mn(NO_3)_2(AR)$ by shaking in air-tight polythene containers, mechanically changing the factors effecting the uptake under investigation each time while other factors were kept constant. The experimental assembly was kept in a thermally insulated cation maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ$ to simulate biological conditions. At the end of the desired period of equilibration the contents were filtered through IG₄

crucible. The residue was washed with doubly distilled water till it was free from the absorbed manganese and the calcium and the manganese contents of the residue were determined⁴.

The effect of the incorporation of manganese on the solubility of bone mineral was carried out with the solubility studies being based exclusively on the microanalytical determination of phosphate⁶ in the samples after equilibration. Potassium acid phthalate-sodium hydroxide and verhol-HCl were used as buffer combinations. The pH was measured with a line-operated Beckman pH meter before and after equilibration to ascertain its constancy. 0.2g of the sample (260 mesh, B. S. S) was added to 100 ml of the buffer solution prepared in carbondioxide-free doubly distilled water, contained in air-tight polythene container and shaken mechanically at regulated speed at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ$. At the desired period of equilibration the samples were separately filtered through IG₄ crucible and the phosphate content in the filtrate was determined complexometrically⁶.

Results and Discussion

The results of uptake of manganese by CaHA are given in Fig. 1. The uptake on Mn^{2+} by CaHA is found to (i) decrease with increase of pH of the medium of equilibration in the physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0, (ii) increase with increase of concentration of Mn^{2+} ion and (iii) increase with decrease in the particle size of CaHA. The uptake of Mn^{2+} is found to be very rapid initially within the first 60 min (8.0 wt%) and remains almost constant thereafter (Fig. 1D). The uptake varies linearly from 11.2 to 15.4 wt% as the concentration of the medium of $Mn(NO_3)_2$ solution increases from 0.01 to 0.1 M (Fig. 1B). Fig. 1C shows that the uptake under a given set of experimental conditions increases from 19.2 to 21.8 wt% as the mean radius of the particles decreases from 320μ to 60μ .

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Fig. 1.

The fact that the exchange increases with a decrease in the particle size of CaHA (Fig. 1C) and with an increase in Mn²⁺ concentration (Fig. 1B) leads to the conclusion that the first rapid stage is surface-dependent and the second stage of the exchange may be diffusion-controlled and hence slow.

The results of incorporation of Mn²⁺ on the solubility of bone mineral are given in Fig. 2. The dependence of solubility on (i) the pH of medium of equilibration over physiologically important range of 5.0 to 8.0 and (ii) the manganese content in the sample, at a given pH was investigated. It was observed that (i) the solubility of given sample decreased with increase of pH of the dissolving medium (Fig. 2B), which was due to the proton accepting tendency of (PO₄)³⁻ in the dissolving medium⁶ and (ii) at a given pH the solubility decreased initially and increased above 40% mole concentration of manganese in the solid solution (Fig. 2A). This observation can be explained on the basis of (i) the common ion effect applied to solubility products of the solid solutions according to

Milhofer⁷ and (ii) due to the formation of covalent bonds on the introduction of Mn²⁺ in CaHA⁸. This explains the role of incorporation of Mn²⁺ in the solubility of the bone mineral.

Fig. 2.

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